

Persuasive Communication Factors and Their Effect on COVID-19 Vaccine Acceptance Amongst Residents of the Informal Urban Settlement in Kenya

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Abstract:

Despite the immense resources and intensified interventions by the government and the international community, the desired uptake of the COVID-19 vaccine in Kenya has not been commendable. Hesitancy toward the COVID-19 vaccine remains high among the Kenyan population. Misconception and negative publicity have widely affected vaccine uptake. Since the vaccine is now readily available in the country's private and public health facilities, it is critical to convince those hesitant to take it. Persuasive communication plays a critical role in the messaging framework during a public health crisis. They mostly rely on various

communication channels, communication sources, and messaging structures to convey the public health message at different levels and to various targets. Given the expansive information environment, we sought to characterize the use of persuasive communication factors for COVID-19 vaccine information and determine their effect on vaccine acceptance. This study evaluated persuasive communication factors and their effect on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya. A quantitative cross-sectional study was conducted in the informal urban settlement of Kibera. Data was collected using a structured pretested questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Demographic variables were analyzed and presented using means and proportions. The results indicated that trustworthiness/expertise ($\beta = 0.175$, $p = 0.001$), attractiveness/likability ($\beta = 0.120$, $p = 0.009$), and familiarity/similarity ($\beta = 0.165$, $p = 0.001$) significantly affected the likelihood of vaccine acceptance. Message factors such as factual/logical appeals ($\beta = 0.829$, $p = 0.000$) significantly and positively affected the likelihood of vaccination. Channel factors such as interactivity ($\beta = 0.439$, $p = 0.000$) and decidability ($\beta = 0.287$, $p = 0.019$) significantly positively affected the likelihood of vaccination. The study found that trustworthiness/expertise, attractiveness/likability, familiarity/similarity, factual/logical appeals, interactivity, and decidability significantly affect vaccine acceptance. These findings can inform policymakers, public health professionals, and communication experts on effective communication strategies to enhance vaccine uptake in informal urban settlements.

Keywords: *vaccination, COVID-19, informal urban settlements, Kibera.*

Introduction

Vaccination is one of the most successful public health interventions and a cornerstone for preventing communicable infectious diseases (Andre et al., 2008). Notwithstanding vaccine progress, ongoing public acceptance is required to maintain herd immunity, prevent outbreaks of vaccine-preventable illnesses, and ensure the adoption of novel vaccines (Callender, 2016). The COVID-19 vaccine has been met with a mix of excitement and apprehension.

Therefore, behavior change (behavior to prevent transmission and infection) is the only feasible intervention measure to combat this public health emergency (Figueroa, 2017). Although different countries have launched strategic battles against the virus in different ways, there is no doubt that publicizing and encouraging the public to undertake effective preventive actions is one of the important measures. It is self-evident that communication campaigns play a critical role in improving public health by keeping people well-informed about health communication and encouraging people to take preventive measures (Hong & Kim, 2020). One way to achieve the desired behavioral change is by using persuasive messages. Gass and Seiter (2011) generally describe persuasion as any attempt at changing the attitudes, motivations, beliefs, and behaviors of one or many individuals (Gass & Seiter, 2011).

Persuasion strategies can be used to seek behavioral change, and in the world of mass persuasion, these strategies are applied in the shape of campaigns, be it of social, health, or environmental nature. Persuasive messages in health communication campaigns frequently utilise a basic expectancy–value mechanism by designing messages to influence beliefs regarding the subjective likelihood of various outcomes occurring: attitudinal and behavioral effects are contingent upon each individual valuation of those outcomes (Atkin & Rice, 2013).

During a pandemic, a health communication campaign is structured to enable individuals to receive information from multiple

communication channels (Piltch-Loeb et al., 2018). These channels are relied upon by risk communicators to push out a message, and the public pulls on that communication and pushes it to their own network (Mheidly & Fares, 2020), (Steffens et al., 2020).

Kenya planned to fully vaccinate 19 million adults (70% of the adult population) by the end of June 2022 and the entire adult population of 27 million people by the end of the year 2022. During the same period, it also aimed to fully vaccinate 2.9 million teenagers aged 15-17 years (50% of the population) and the entire teenage population of 5.8 million by the end of December 2022.

Despite efforts by the government to upscale COVID-19 vaccination uptake a paltry 31.2 % had been fully vaccinated by 9 June 2022. To achieve COVID-19 vaccination targets of the entire adult population of 27 million people by the end of the year, the government needed to be strategic in its persuasive communication.

The specific objectives of the study are listed below;

- To assess the effect of source factors on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance amongst residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya.
- To evaluate the effect of messages factors on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance amongst residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya.
- To examine the effect of channel factors on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance amongst residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted at the Kibera informal settlement which comprises 14 villages with a population of 149,662 individuals. The area covers approximately 12.1 km², and is densely

populated with 15,311 persons per square kilometer.

Study Design

A cross-sectional research design involving quantitative data collection was used.

Sampling Frame

The sampling frame for this study consisted of a list of all residents of the Kibera slum area (Kenya Population & Housing Census, 2019).

Sampling Technique

The study used stratified random sampling. The strata comprised of the Kibera informal settlement residents. Proportionate stratification was used to select the sample size per sub-location.

To ensure a representative sample of each Kibera village, the sample size was calculated separately. A sample of 149,662 participants at a confidence level of 95%, a confidence interval of ± 5 , adjusted for missing responses, was required.

Members were picked using stratified random sampling. To ensure representativeness, members were stratified by sex, village, and probability proportion to size. Since the proportions of male-to-female residents in Kibera is nearly equal, the study included 192 male and 192 female students in the study.

While in the 14 villages, the study identified a landmark and then targeted households in these localities. From the identified landmark, we interviewed our targets in all directions. The landmark was our starting point.

Sample Size

The sample size for this study was determined using the sample table developed by Krejcie and Morgan formula developed in 1970. We assumed the confidence level to be at 95% and a precision $\pm 5\%$ (Tuner, 2003). In this study, the population size is 149,662. The following

Simple random sampling was then used to select the number of residents per sub-location. Therefore, the sample size of this study was 384 residents. The stratified random sampling is represented in Table 1.

Table 1. The Sample Size

Sub location in Kibera	Population	Sample Size	Percentage
Kibera	64,754	166	43.27
Sarang'ombe	55,303	142	36.95
Laini Saba	29,605	76	19.78
Total	149,662	384	100.00

Source: KNBS (2019)

Data Collection Technique

The study used an interviewer to administer the pre-tested questionnaires. Well-trained research assistants were enlisted to manage a pretested questionnaire for the residents. A questionnaire was developed to elicit responses relevant to the aim of the study.

Data Management and Analysis

Data Entry and Storage

Data was collected on paper questionnaires. Epi-info version 7.2.5.0e was used to create a make view for data entry.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done with the software "Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23". The analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistics. Polit and Beck (2012:379) detailed that descriptive

statistics are used to describe and synthesize data.

Descriptive statistical procedures such as tables, graphs, and proportions were utilized to report and describe findings, and regression models were used to test the research questions. The responses from respondents were quantified whereas the levels of measurements and data were synthesized to calculate averages, frequencies, and percentages. A multiple linear regression was applied to examine persuasive communication factors and their effect on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance amongst residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya as follows:

$$Y \text{ (COVID-19 vaccine acceptance)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Source factors}) + \beta_2(\text{Messages factors}) + \beta_3(\text{Channel factors}) + \epsilon$$

In this equation, β_0 represents the intercept, β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are the coefficients that show the impact of each independent variable on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance, and ϵ is the error term representing the unexplained variance.

Results

Response Rate

This survey targeted to interview 384 participants, but only 329 participants agreed to participate in the study.

The response rate for this study is 85.68%.

Descriptive Statistics

Participants were almost equally distributed between male (50.5%), and female (49.5%). Regarding level of education, it was distributed as follows, secondary education (33.1%), tertiary/college education (29.5%), university education (25.5%), and primary education (11.9%). Most (42.9%) of the participants were aged 31-40 years, with (21.9%) aged 41-50 years (25.5%) aged 18- 30 years, and (9.7%) aged 51 years and above (table 2).

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency n(%)
Gender	
Female	163 (49.5%)
Male	166 (50.5%)
Education	
Primary or below	39 (11.9%)
Secondary	109 (33.1%)
Tertiary/College	97 (29.5%)
University	84 (25.5%)
Age	
18-30	84 (25.5%)
31-40	141 (42.9%)
41-50	72 (21.9%)
51-or older	32 (9.7%)

The participants were asked to indicate which COVID-19 sources of information they considered. Most of the participants indicated that they consider healthcare practitioners 163 (49.5%) as sources of vaccination information, government officials 89 (27.1%), peers 47 (14.3%), and religious leaders 30 (9.1%)

Reliability Analysis

A Cronbach alpha coefficient statistic was computed to evaluate the reliability of the data collected. The findings indicate that Cronbach's alpha is 0.873, which indicates a high level of internal consistency for our scale, thus, the questionnaire is reliable. According to Lavrakas (2008), a Cronbach alpha (above 0.7) indicates that the data collection instrument is reliable.

Table 3. Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.873	.873	4

A majority of the participants indicated that they were very likely 221 (67.2%) to accept the COVID-19 vaccine, 84 (25.5%) were not sure whether they would accept or decline to be vaccinated, and 24 (7.3%) indicated that they were very unlikely to accept the vaccine.

Of the 24 participants who indicated that they were very unlikely to take the COVID-19 vaccine, 13 (54.2%) indicated that the refusal was due to cultural and religious beliefs, COVID-19

campaign messages are not sufficient 8 (33.3%), and 3 (12.5%) indicated that it was due to the long queues at the health facilities.

Inferential Statistics

An ANOVA test was conducted to evaluate if the likelihood of accepting the COVID-19

vaccine depended on the source of information. The findings below indicate that the source of the COVID-19 information had no significant effect on whether an individual was likely to be vaccinated ($F(3, 324) = 1.367, p = 0.000$).

Table 4. ANOVA Results

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.556	3	.519	1.367	.253
Within Groups	122.920	324	.379		
Total	124.476	327			

To evaluate the objectives for this study, regression models were fitted.

Specific objective 1: A regression model was fit between the likelihood of vaccine acceptance and the characteristics of the communication sources.

It is evident that the attributes of the source had a significant effect on the likelihood of an individual accepting a vaccine. The results indicate that the attributes like trustworthiness/expertise had a significant and

positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination ($\beta = 0.175, p = 0.001$). The source being attractive/likable also has a significant positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination ($\beta = 0.120, p = 0.009$). Moreover, the source being familiar/similar also had a significant positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination ($\beta = 0.165, p = 0.001$). Factors such as power ($\beta = 0.025, p = 0.620$) had a positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination, but the effect was not significant at the 5% level of significance.

Table 5. Model 1

<i>Coefficients</i>					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	.531	.221		2.405	.017
trustworthy/ expertise	.175	.051	.219	3.420	.001
Powerful	.025	.049	.030	.497	.620
Attractive/likable	.120	.046	.151	2.612	.009
familiar/ similar	.165	.049	.201	3.390	.001

Note: a. Dependent Variable: After exposure to COVID-19 vaccination messages, what will be your decision/what was your decision towards vaccine acceptance?

Objective 1 suggests that the attributes of the communication sources have a significant impact on vaccine acceptance. The regression model shows that trustworthiness/expertise, attractiveness/likability, and familiarity/similarity of the source have a significant and positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination. This finding is consistent with

previous studies that have identified these characteristics as important factors in persuasive communication. The trustworthiness and expertise of the source can increase the credibility of the message and influence an individual's decision to accept the vaccine (Kreuter & McClure, 2004). Attractive and likable sources can increase the likability of the

message and create a positive attitude towards vaccination (Yuan et al., 2019). In addition, familiar or similar sources may also increase the likelihood of vaccine acceptance, as individuals may feel more comfortable and relate better to someone who is similar to them (Yaqub et al., 2014).

Specific Objective 2: A regression model was also fit between the likelihood of vaccination and the message appeals. Based on the findings in

table 6, messages with factual/logical appeal had a significant positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination ($\beta = 0.829$, $p = 0.000$). Messages with fear appeals had a positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination ($\beta = 0.316$, $p = 0.104$), but this effect was not significant. On the other hand, messages with emotional appeals had a negative effect on the likelihood of vaccination ($\beta = -0.109$, $p = 0.428$) however, this negative effect was not significant.

Table 6. Model 2

<i>Coefficients</i>						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	Constant	1.790	.229		7.805	.000
	Fear Appeals	.316	.194	.113	1.631	.104
	Factual/ Logical Appeals	.829	.228	.250	3.630	.000
	Emotional Appeals	-.109	.137	-.044	-.794	.428

Note: a. Dependent Variable: After exposure to COVID-19 vaccination messages, what will be your decision/what was your decision towards vaccine acceptance?

The results show that messages with factual/logical appeal had a significant positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination, while fear appeals, and emotional appeals had no significant effect. This finding is consistent with the idea that messages that provide clear and accurate information can increase the perceived benefits of vaccination and reduce perceived risks (Lipkus, 2007). Fear appeals may also be effective in some cases, as they can increase perceived susceptibility and severity of a disease, but this was not significant in this study. Emotional appeals may not be effective as they may not provide enough information and can create confusion and uncertainty.

Specific objective 3: A regression model between the likelihood of vaccination and the characteristics of the communication channels was fitted to evaluate objective 3. The findings indicated that channel characteristics such as interactivity ($\beta = 0.439$, $p = 0.000$) and decodability ($\beta = 0.287$, $p = 0.019$) have a significant positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination. Specializability ($\beta = 0.246$, $p = 0.070$) had a positive effect on an individual's likelihood to be vaccinated, but the effect was not significant.

Table 7. Model 3

<i>Coefficients</i>						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	2.232	.108		20.676	.000
	Interactivity	.439	.112	.332	3.913	.000
	Credibility	-.066	.177	-.023	-.375	.708
	Accessibility	-.053	.147	-.022	-.362	.718

Specialisability	.246	.135	.117	1.821	.070
Decodability	.287	.121	.181	2.363	.019

Note: a. Dependent Variable: After exposure to COVID-19 vaccination messages, what will be your decision/what was your decision towards vaccine acceptance?

The results show that interactivity and decodability of the communication channels had a significant positive effect on the likelihood of vaccination, while specialisability had no significant effect. Interactivity allows for two-way communication and can increase engagement and involvement in the vaccination decision-making process (Baram-Tsabari & Schejter, 2019). Decodability refers to the clarity and ease of understanding of the message, which can increase the likelihood of message acceptance (Rowan, 1991).

Persuasive Communication Factors and COVID-19 Vaccine Acceptance

The researcher used a multiple linear regression to examine persuasive communication factors and their effect on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance amongst residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya.

Table 8 presents the summary of the regression model used to examine the effect of various factors on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlement in Kenya.

Table 8. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.891 ^a	.794	.792	3.66116

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), channel factors, source factors, message factors

From table 8, The correlation coefficient between the predicted values and the actual values of COVID-19 vaccine acceptance was 0.891, indicating a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination was 0.794, suggesting that 79.4% of the variance in COVID-19 vaccine acceptance can be explained by the independent variables included in the model.

Table 9 provides important information about the overall fit and significance of the regression model used to examine the effect of various

factors on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya.

Table 9, the F-value (415.457) indicates the significance of the overall model in explaining the variation in COVID-19 vaccine acceptance. The significance level (0.000) suggests that the model is statistically significant, indicating that the included factors have a significant impact on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya.

Table 9. ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16706.516	3	5568.839	415.457	.000 ^b
	Residual	4342.936	324	13.404		
	Total	21049.451	327			

Note: a. Dependent Variable: covid19 vaccine acceptance; b. Predictors: (Constant), channel factors, source factors, messages factors

Overall, Table 9 demonstrates that the regression model used in the study is statistically significant and provides valuable insights into the factors influencing COVID-19 vaccine acceptance in the informal urban settlement in Kenya.

Table 10 shows the coefficients for the multiple linear regression model. The model aimed to predict the acceptance of the COVID-19 vaccine based on source factors, message factors, and channel factors.

Table 10. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	9.799	2.264		4.328	.000
Source factors	.146	.072	.056	2.043	.042
Messages factors	2.327	.069	.916	33.512	.000
Channel factors	.420	.095	.112	4.405	.000

Note: a. Dependent Variable: covid19 vaccine acceptance

From the results in table 10, the following multiple linear regression was established:

$$Y (\text{covid19 vaccine acceptance}) = 9.799 + 0.146 (\text{source factors}) + 2.327 (\text{messages factors}) + 0.420 (\text{channel factors})$$

The coefficient for source factors was 0.146, indicating a positive relationship between source factors and COVID-19 vaccine acceptance. The coefficient for messages factors was 2.327, indicating a strong positive relationship between messages factors and COVID-19 vaccine acceptance. The coefficient for channel factors was 0.420, indicating a positive relationship between channel factors and COVID-19 vaccine acceptance.

These coefficients represent the impact of each independent variable on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance. The positive coefficients for source factors, messages factors, and channel factors suggest that these factors have a significant influence on vaccine acceptance among residents of the informal urban settlement in Kenya. Specifically, the messages factors had the strongest impact, followed by channel factors and source factors.

This finding asserted that the content and delivery of messages, as well as the communication channels used, play crucial roles in influencing vaccine acceptance in the informal

urban settlement in Kenya. These findings highlight the importance of effective communication strategies in promoting COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya.

Discussion

Specific objective 1 aimed to investigate the impact of source attributes on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance within informal urban settlements in Kenya. The regression analysis unveiled compelling results, affirming the substantial influence of source characteristics on vaccination likelihood. Trustworthiness and expertise of the information source emerged as a potent driver, significantly and positively affecting the likelihood of vaccination. This underscores the pivotal role of credibility and competence in shaping public attitudes towards vaccines. Furthermore, the source's attractiveness and likability were found to have a significant positive impact on vaccine acceptance. This suggests that individuals are more receptive to vaccine-related information when it is conveyed by sources they find appealing, emphasizing the role of personal connection and positive feelings towards the messenger. Familiarity and similarity of the information source also had a significant positive effect on vaccination likelihood, underlining the

importance of relatability and comfort in influencing vaccine decisions. This finding highlights the critical role of source credibility, likability, and relatability in effectively promoting COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya.

Specific objective 2 aimed to assess the impact of different message appeals on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance within informal urban settlements in Kenya. The regression analysis revealed intriguing insights. Messages with factual and logical appeal significantly and positively influenced the likelihood of vaccination, emphasizing the importance of clear and accurate information in persuading individuals to accept the vaccine. However, fear appeals, despite having a positive effect, did not reach statistical significance, suggesting that instilling fear alone may not be a strong motivator for vaccine acceptance in this context. Surprisingly, messages with emotional appeals had a negative effect on vaccination likelihood, although this negative impact was not statistically significant. These findings underscore the critical role of providing well-founded and logical information in effective vaccine communication, while also suggesting that fear-based and emotional appeals may require careful implementation and contextual adaptation to be effective.

Specific objective 3 aimed to explore the influence of communication channel characteristics on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance within informal urban settlements in Kenya. The regression analysis yielded significant insights. Communication channels with high interactivity, which facilitate two-way communication and engagement, had a substantial positive impact on the likelihood of vaccination. This suggests that channels enabling dialogue and discussion might enhance the decision-making process regarding vaccines. Additionally, channels with greater decodability, characterized by clear and easily understandable messages, positively affected vaccine acceptance. This highlights the importance of delivering information in a comprehensible manner to the target audience. While specialisability, which relates to tailoring information to specific

groups, also had a positive effect, it did not reach statistical significance in this context. This underscores the potential benefit of personalized communication but suggests that further investigation may be needed to determine its full impact on vaccine acceptance. This finding emphasizes the significance of interactive and easily comprehensible communication channels in promoting COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya.

Finally, the study aimed to investigate the persuasive communication factors influencing COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya. Using multiple linear regression, the results demonstrated a strong positive relationship between the predicted and actual values of COVID-19 vaccine acceptance, with a correlation coefficient of 0.891. This suggests that these factors indeed have a substantial impact on vaccine acceptance. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) at 0.794 indicates that 79.4% of the variation in vaccine acceptance can be explained by the factors studied. Further analysis revealed that the model itself was statistically significant, as indicated by the F-value of 415.457, signifying that the combined influence of source factors, message factors, and channel factors significantly explains the variation in vaccine acceptance. Notably, message factors had the most substantial impact, with a coefficient of 2.327, followed by channel factors (0.420) and source factors (0.146). These findings underscore the pivotal role of effective communication strategies, both in terms of message content and delivery channels, in promoting COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya.

Conclusion

This study has highlighted the significance of persuasive communication factors in promoting COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya. However, several avenues for future research

could be explored to extend the findings of this study. First, future research should examine the influence of socio-demographic characteristics such as age, gender, income, and education on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya. Second, future research should explore the impact of cultural beliefs and attitudes toward vaccines on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya. Third, future research should examine the influence of political factors such as government policies and communication strategies on COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya. Fourth, future research should focus on the effectiveness of different interventions and communication strategies to promote COVID-19 vaccine acceptance among residents of informal urban settlements in Kenya.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

Andre, F., Booy, R., Bock, H., Clemens, J., Datta, S., John, T., Lee, B., Lolekha, S., Peltola, H., Ruff, T., Santosham, M., & Schmitt, H. (2008). Vaccination greatly reduces disease, disability, death and inequity worldwide. *Bulletin*

of the World Health Organization, 86(2), 140–146. <https://doi.org/10.2471/BLT.07.040089>

Atkin, C. K., & Rice, R. E. (2013). Theory and Principles of Public Communication Campaigns. In *Public Communication Campaigns* (Fourth Edition, pp. 2–19). SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781544308449>

Baram-Tsabari, A., & Schejter, A. (2019). The Double-Edged Sword of New Media in Supporting Public Engagement with Science. In Y. Kali, A. Schejter, & A. Baram-Tsabari (Eds.), *Learning in a Networked Society: Computer Supported Collaborative Learning* (CSCL) book series. Springer

Callender, D. (2016). Vaccine hesitancy: More than a movement. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 12(9), 2464–2468. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645515.2016.1178434>

Figueroa, M. E. (2017). A Theory-Based Socioecological Model of Communication and Behavior for the Containment of the Ebola Epidemic in Liberia. *Journal of Health Communication*, 22(sup1), 5–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730.2016.1231725>

Gass, R. H., & Seiter, J. S. (2011). *Persuasion, Social Influence, and Compliance Gaining*. Allyn & Bacon.

Hong, Y., & Kim, S. (2020). Influence of Presumed Media Influence for Health Prevention: How Mass Media Indirectly Promote Health Prevention Behaviors through Descriptive Norms. *Health Communication*, 35(14), 1800–1810. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2019.1663585>

Johnson, B., & Turner, L. A. (2003). *Data Collection Strategies in Mixed Methods Research*. SAGE.

KNBS (2019) 2019 Kenya population and housing census volume 1: population census volume 1: population by county and sub-county. Retrieved from <https://www.knbs.or.ke/?wpdmpromo=2019->

[kenya-population-and-housing-census-volume-i-population-by-county-and-sub-county](#)

Kreuter, M. W., & McClure, S. M. (2004). The role of culture in health communication. *Annual review of public health*, 25, 439–455. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.publhealth.25.101802.123000>

Lavrakas, P. (2008). *Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods*. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963947>.

Lipkus I. M. (2007). Numeric, verbal, and visual formats of conveying health risks: suggested best practices and future recommendations. *Medical decision making : an international journal of the Society for Medical Decision Making*, 27(5), 696–713. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272989X07307271>

Lou, Chen & Yuan, Shupe. (2018). Influencer Marketing: How Message Value and Credibility Affect Consumer Trust of Branded Content on Social Media. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 19, 1-45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15252019.2018.1533501>

Maiman, L. A., & Becker, M. H. (1974). The Health Belief Model: Origins and Correlates in Psychological Theory. *Health Education Monographs*, 2(4), 336–353. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019817400200404>

Mheidly, N., & Fares, J. (2020). Leveraging media and health communication strategies to overcome the COVID-19 infodemic. *Journal of Public Health Policy*, 41(4), 410–420. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41271-020-00247-w>

Piltch-Loeb, R., Merdjanoff, A. A., & Abramson, D. M. (2018). How the US Population Engaged with and Prioritized Sources of Information about the Emerging Zika Virus in 2016. *Health Security*, 16(3), 165–177. [c10.1089/hs.2017.0107](https://doi.org/10.1089/hs.2017.0107)

Polit, D., & Beck, C. (2012). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice* (9th ed.). Philadelphia, PA: Wolters Kluwer Health/Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

Rowan, K.E. (1991). Goals, Obstacles, and Strategies in Risk Communication: A Problem-solving Approach to Improving Communication about Risks. *Journal of Applied Communication Research* 19(4), 300–329. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00909889109365311>

Steffens, M. S., Dunn, A. G., Leask, J., & Wiley, K. E. (2020). Using social media for vaccination promotion: Practices and challenges. *Digital Health*, 6, 2055207620970785. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2055207620970785>